

Supporting Information to

What difference can drop-in substitution actually make? A life cycle assessment of alternative water repellent chemicals.

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S1 Details on the DWR technical system

S1.1 The DWR product (chemical mixture)

Commercial durable water repellent (DWR) products are chemical mixtures containing several components, in addition to the water repellent ingredient, the DWR product also contains carriers and dispersing agents (Holmquist *et al.* 2016 Tab. S1). Examples of DWR product ingredients are listed in Table S1, with example ranges taken from selected material safety data sheets (MSDS). Co-solvents have two main functions; (1) to lower the surface tension of water in the formulation and help the wetting process in the application of the DWR emulsion and (2) improve coalescence (the "melting together") of the emulsion droplets during the drying process and help to form a continuous polymer film on the fiber surface. Highly volatile co-solvents (e.g. acetone) is also used to help with the water evaporation (under formation of an azeotrope mixture) which can be especially important if the DWR formulations are applied under conditions of high air humidity (e.g. in Asia). Dispersing agents work as surfactants at the emulsion droplet/water interface with electrostatic (ionic) and steric (non-ionic) stabilization. They help to keep a "distance" between the emulsion droplets (the DWR polymers) and are essential for a good distribution of polymers on the textile weave.

Table S1 Typical ingredients in a DWR formulation. The DWR product can also contain biocides and catalysts.

Category	Content range	Chemical, example
Water repellent	5-75%	Side-chain fluorinated polymers
Cosolvent	0.1-7%	Ethylene glycol, ethoxylated alcohols
Cosolvent (high volatility)	0.1-10%	Acetone, methanol
Dispersing agent	0.1-5%	Surfactants; fatty alcohol polyglycol ether, hexadecyldimethylamine

The water repellent ingredient is commonly a co-polymer (Holmquist *et al.* 2016). The exact chemical composition of that co-polymer is generally a trade secret, but it can be e.g. an acrylate basis and contain different functional structural elements to provide water repellency, film forming, cross-linking, soft hand etc.

S1.2 Finishing process

Conventionally the DWR is applied to the fabric by a wet treatment process where the fabric is dipped in the DWR containing solution, padded in foulards and dried and cured (Kissa 2001). The DWR finishing may require additional process wash and drying (Kissa 2001), but in continuous processes this is not needed and water emissions are restricted to system losses and water from cleaning of the equipment (European Commission 2003). Alternatively plasma technology can be used, either to apply the DWR to the fabric or to activate the surface chemistry of the fabric prior to DWR application to reduce the amount of DWR needed (Mahltig 2015). Other application techniques are spraying or by exhaust (Kissa 2001).

The DWR formulation need to be combined with several other chemical products in order to achieve appropriate water (and oil) repellency:

- Crosslinkers are commonly applied to DWR systems. A crosslinker, or a booster, is used to improve structure by aiding the formation of the water (and oil) repellent film on the textile fibers, and increase its stability for e.g. improved wash fastness (Mahltig 2015). Common crosslinker systems are based on isocyanates or melamine.
- Network forming agents can be added to decrease the temperatures needed in the curing step to achieve oil repellency (Mahltig 2015).
- Catalyst to activate inactive crosslinking groups (always needed for the melamine-based systems). The same function can be achieved by the application of heat for certain systems. The products termed catalysts in this context can also have other properties than catalytic, in silicone based system catalysts aid the film forming and proper orientation of the silicone polymer, e.g. by affecting sorption and orientation of the polymer (Kissa 2001).
- For DWR systems not containing silicones, softeners may need to be added (Kissa 2001).
- Lubricants, such as e.g. non-ionic polyethylene dispersions, may also be needed to improve sewing properties (Kissa 2001).
- Wetting agents to reduce penetration problems.

The combination of DWR product and auxiliary textile chemicals will be brand specific as each manufacturer recommends a recipe for the finishing bath. In addition, each finisher adjusts this recipe to fit their machinery and products. In the present study a generalized combination of DWR and auxiliary chemicals has been modelled, aiming to capture the potential effects relevant for the different DWR systems rather than specific products and brands.

S2 Details on the technical performance testing

S2.1 ISO standards for technical performance testing

ISO 4920:2012 Determination of resistance to surface wetting (spray test)

ISO 14419:2010 Oil repellency-Hydrocarbon resistance test

ISO 26330:2012 Domestic washing and drying procedures for textile testing

ISO 12947-2:2016 Determination of the abrasion resistance of fabrics by the Martindale method

ISO 4892-3:2016 Accelerated aging via of exposure to laboratory light sources in controlled humid environment

S2.2 The spray rating test (ISO 4920:2012)

The pattern of the water remaining drops on the fabric's surface is visually judged according to standardized dimensionless spray test ratings (ISO 5 = not sticking or wetting of the upper surface to ISO 1= complete wetting of the upper surface). A score of three (ISO 3= wetting of the upper surface at spray points) was set as the limit for when the functional unit (FU) was achieved, and at least one DWR product in each category met this criterion after laundry.

S3 Emission scenarios

The DWR products are complex with several ingredients. In addition, all chemical products contain impurities depending on class, i.e. analytical grade or technical grade. All chemicals included in the DWR formulation or used for its manufacture can be released, during the manufacture and in the later life cycle stages; the use phase and end-of-life. Further, breakdown products may be released into the environment during the life cycle. In the present study generalized emission scenarios were created and applied to arrive at a life cycle inventory (LCI) for each DWR system.

S3.1 Manufacturing

In chemical production, at minimum, the cleaning of the equipment will generate wastewater but the emissions are highly dependent on the type industrial activity (European Commission 2006). In textile manufacture the wet treatment is often water-based and generates large volumes of wastewater (e.g. Khan and Malik 2014). Emissions generated during manufacturing will vary depending on i) product/substance properties, ii) type of industry and iii) with manufacturing location, i.e. where in the world and under what legislation the manufacturing takes place. In the EU, under the Industry Emissions Directive (IED), there are reference documents available describing best available technique (BAT), from an environmental protection perspective, the so called BREF. BAT includes both the selection of chemicals, the reductions of their use and reduction of emissions. In the present study, the BREFs, together with results and procedures as reported by Roos *et al.* (2019) were used as a starting point to establish emission scenarios.

S3.1.1 Emission scenarios

Adequate LCIs for chemical production and use are often missing (Hischier *et al.* 2005), in particular chemical emissions are difficult to account for and those are often missing completely. There are however a number of studies published suggesting models to redeem this situation, e.g. by the application of generic emission factors (Jiménez-González *et al.* 2000, Geisler *et al.* 2004, Hischier *et al.* 2005, Wernet *et al.* 2012, Roos *et al.* 2019). In the following emission factors reported in the literature is described together with other data relevant for the establishment of emission scenarios.

- Emission factors to air vary between 0.02 and 0.0000001 (fraction of input) in the life cycle assessment (LCA) literature for chemical production (Jiménez-González *et al.* 2000, Geisler *et al.* 2004, Hischier *et al.* 2005), while it is set to 0.15 in the generic, un-abated, worst case scenario for “wide dispersive indoor use, inclusion into or onto a matrix” in a risk assessment context (ECHA 2016). In some cases, air emission factors are set based on volatility criteria and in other cases the emission factors are applied across all chemicals. Emission factors across DWR systems have been measured to be 1-5% based on organic carbon emissions (European Commission 2003; Appendix IV Table 10). In addition to generic air emissions Roos *et al.* (2019) assumed that 1% of polymers are degraded to monomers during textile manufacture operations, generating air emissions.

- Emissions factors to water were not very well described in the literature. Emissions to surface water depend on the fraction of liquid waste that is directed to wastewater and the efficiency of the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) treatment. In textile manufacture water emissions are highly dependent on the fate of the spent baths from the wet treatment. Emissions are also different between auxiliaries and property lending substances.
 - Substances with high reactivity with air or water generate emissions of the reaction product unless complete mineralization is achieved. Roos *et al.* (2019) assumed 90% removal by reaction for such compounds.
 - Roos *et al.* (2019) further assumed that 0.001% of the content in the chemical product is degraded to common breakdown products and that inorganic salts are not degraded and are soluble ions.
 - In chemical product manufacture liquid emissions constitute yield losses and coupled by-products, as well as solvent waste (Jiménez-González *et al.* 2000). Jiménez-González *et al.* (2000) applied yield losses as 3-13% with no major side product and 13-23% with major side product.
 - Chemical oxygen demand (COD) in wastewaters have been measured to 2% of the yearly batch (European Commission 2006 Table 4.21).
 - In formulation 0.1% product loss has been documented due to rinsing of the equipment (European Commission 2006 Table 2.19).
 - Roos *et al.* (2019) assumed that 95% of property lending substances stay on the product while the worst case emission factor applicable for textile finishing in risk assessment was 0.3 (ECHA 2016) when the chemical is included into the article and 1 when it is not included into the article.
 - Wernet *et al.* (2012) states that a 90% reduction of the pollutant load can be expected from wastewater treatment, based on data in Köhler *et al.* (2007), which describes rather extensive/advanced wastewater treatment. Removal in on-site WWTPs, measured with the summary variable COD, are in the range 84-96% in the textile manufacturing industry (European Commission 2003 Table 4.41), and 83-100% in the chemical industry (European Commission 2006 Table 3.3). Paired measurements on individual substances are rare but indicate that individual removal rates vary greatly. In Swedish municipal WWTPs the median removal rate was shown to be 19% when pharmaceuticals and some other compounds were measured (S-EPA 2008 Table 18).
- Soil emission factors are rare in the literature, for chemical manufacture an emission factor of 0.0001 is listed in the risk assessment guidance (ECHA 2016) but in the LCA related literature no emission factors have been found. Land application rates for sludges from municipal WWTPs varies greatly between regions (LeBlanc *et al.* 2008, Mateo-Sagasta *et al.* 2015). Degradability also varies, depending on substance properties and treatment processes.

Emissions were accounted for by a generic basic scenario, aiming to capture an average case. Emission factors (EmF) for the respective scenarios are listed in Table S2. The emission scenarios are not aiming to capture any specific facility. The emission scenarios are anchored in the data as presented above, with priority to the data from Roos *et al.*

(2019) as that is the dataset used for the LCI of the synthetic weaves in the full LCA on DWR impregnated outdoor garments. Note that the emissions scenarios do not make up a complete mass balance as air losses are not subtracted from the main product flow. The emission scenarios apply to the chemicals used in each process and impurities (when assessed relevant, here based on Holmquist *et al.* (2016)). Emission factors are applied on the process where the chemical is used, although the actual emissions may occur at a later stage, e.g. if carry over of chemicals from wet treatment generate emissions during curing due to the elevated temperature. Increased volatilization by the heated conditions in some process steps is not considered as the volatilized substances will condensate again at ambient temperatures. In the finishing processes the DWR active ingredient and crosslinker were treated as a property lending chemicals while all auxiliary chemicals were assumed to be emitted to 100% (emission reaching the environment further reduced by emission factors in Table S2). Degradation products and impurities were modelled based on Holmquist *et al.* (2016), Holmquist *et al.* (2020).

Table S2 Emission factors (EmF) for the basic emission scenarios. EmFs are dimensionless and are the fraction of the chemical used (that do not stay on the fabric; property lending chemicals) that is emitted to the respective compartment. Polymers were treated as non-volatile substances.

Emission compartment/ Manufacturing stage	Chemical production	Textile processing
Air	2%, only volatile substances* <i>EmF 0.02</i>	2%, only volatile substances* <i>EmF 0.02</i>
Water	10% emission and 90% separation in WWTP <i>EmF 0.01</i>	90% separation in WWTP <i>EmF 0.1</i>
Soil	All waste [#] properly treated, generating no emissions 90% of sludge is incinerated, generating no emissions, and 10% of sludge is land applied, degradation not considered <i>EmF 0.009</i>	All waste [#] properly treated, generating no emissions 90% of sludge is incinerated, generating no emissions, and 10% of sludge is land applied, degradation not considered <i>EmF 0.09</i>
<p><i>Comments:</i> * A VOC is any organic compound having an initial boiling point less than or equal to 250° C measured at a standard atmospheric pressure of 101.3 kPa (see e.g. DIRECTIVE 2004/42/CE) [#] Waste includes textile specific left-over, chemical products and other material that is not re-used</p>		

S3.2 Diffuse emissions

The diffuse emissions during the use phase (see Figure S1) were modelled based on EmFs as generated within the project, further described below. Emissions from the re-impregnation via wash water were included in the re-impregnation process by application of the textile emission scenario (Table S2) and not further described here.

Fluorotelomer alcohols, perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) and siloxanes on the textile as impurities were modelled to be emitted to air (volatile substances, as defined in Table S2) and water (non-volatile substances) by 25-75 wt%

(the basic scenario was set to 50%) based on results from leaching tests (Ike van der Veen, pers.comm.). This could be a low estimate as weathering studies show that the release on non-polymeric per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) increase after weathering (van der Veen *et al.* 2020).

Polymer emissions via fiber loss during wash has been measured for side-chain fluorinated DWR systems to 0.25 wt% of fluorine for 2-15 washes (here set to 0.02-0.1 wt% per wash, with the basic scenario set to 0.03 wt%), based on the results and model by Schellenberger *et al.* (2019). These emission factors were used to calculate fiber bound DWR emissions to the wash water. Their further fate was calculated by application of fractions to assign fate (83.4% to soil and 5% to water (Schellenberger *et al.* 2019)). Herein, in contrast to Schellenberger *et al.* (2019), all soil emissions were assigned to agricultural land.

Polymer loss from the DWR due to weathering was calculated based on results of a weathering study conducted in Australia (i.e. under extreme exposure conditions generating high losses). Polyamide (PA) textile treated with C4, C6 and C8 side-chain fluorinated polymer based DWRs (see S4.2) were exposed to weathering on a Sydney rooftop over a period of 6 months (Steffen Schellenberger, pers. comm.). Herein the average loss of total fluorine for the C4, C6 and C8 systems (27 wt%) was assumed to be a loss of fiber bound side-chain fluorinated polymers. This fiber loss was scaled to Swedish conditions and the user scenario for the standard jacket by use of insolation data (an important source of uncertainty herein is that the fiber loss might be slower in the beginning when the surface structure of the fabric is not so much effected by weathering, hence the extrapolation done here might lead to overestimations of fiber losses). The monthly average of insolation in Sweden during April-October was 424 MJ/m² (SMHI 2019) and the monthly average in Sydney, during the experimental period, was 646 MJ/m² (BOM 2018). The emission factor was calculated to 0.007 wt% fiber loss m²/MJ by use of Sydney insolation data. Fiber loss in the jacket user scenario was then calculated by multiplication of this emission factor with the total insolation on the jacket per year (247 MJ/m²) to arrive at a 1.75% estimated total loss per year. As the jacket was modelled to be re-impregnated every year fiber losses were modelled as 1.75% of DWR-polymer content on the garment (see S4.7) on a yearly basis. The same emission factor was applied for the ambulance jacket despite its user scenario in theory result in higher insolation, as it is likely that, in practice, the ambulance jacket is not always used outdoors. Emissions were assigned to agricultural soil (due to model technical reasons as characterization factors (CFs) were only implemented for agricultural soil, CFs for natural soil are identical to those for agricultural soil for ecotoxicity and slightly lower for human health). Wash in combination with weathering and abrasion will likely generate higher emissions than those predicted with the approach applied here.

Figure S1: Schematic illustration of the diffuse emissions

S3.3 Modelling of emissions and the further fate

Emissions to air, water and soil can be further sub-divided into a number of compartments, in the environment and in the technosphere. In the USEtox model the following compartments are included: home air, industrial air, urban air, continental air, continental freshwater, continental sea water, natural soil and agricultural soil. In GaBi USEtox characterization factors are partially implemented, there is only one air compartment that is a combination of urban air and continental air (characterization factors are averaged). To ensure consistency the same procedure was applied when new substances were added to the LCA model in GaBi. The exclusion of the indoor air exposure means that potential toxicity due to indoor exposure has not been modelled.

S4 Life cycle inventories (LCIs)

LCIs are intended to be generic and not capture any specific brand or product. Chemical flows were modelled with proxies available in LCA databases, i.e. the LCI tables do not reflect actual product content but a model-product assessed to be representative of a generic product in this context. Mid-values of described ranges were used in the modelling. Emission scenarios as described in Section S3 were applied.

S4.1 Energy requirements for DWR formulation

Product specific data on energy requirements for DWR formulation was challenging to obtain. Instead, all DWRs were modelled to require 0.3, 0.008 and 0.08 kWh/kg of gas, light fuel oil and electricity, respectively, based on environmental reports from one facility.

S4.2 Side-chain fluorinated polymer based DWRs

According to Kissa (2001) fluorochemical repellents can vary with regards to the non-fluorinated parts but have fairly little variations in the fluorine containing moiety of the chemical structures. There are two main commercial processes for the production of fluorinated intermediates for fluorochemical repellents; electrochemical fluorination (ECF) and telomerization (Kissa 2001). The ECF process was developed by 3M and is commonly used to derive perfluorosulfonyl fluorides ($C_nF_{2n+1}SO_2F$), that is an intermediate for the further production of highly fluorinated derivatives (Kissa 2001). The telomerization process was developed by Du Pont. This process generates telomers ($C_2F_2(C_2F_4)_nI$) of varying chain length, that are also, as the sulfonyls, intermediates for further production of highly fluorinated derivatives. The final products, as well as their intermediates, are commonly classified according to the length of the perfluorinated alkyl moiety. C8-DWR denotes 8 carbons in the perfluoroalkyl side chains in the side chain polymer DWR, C6 denotes 6 carbons and C4 denotes 4 carbons.

With the discovery that so-called long chain PFAAs are bioaccumulating (Vierke *et al.* 2012), those, and their pre-cursors, are currently being phased out. C8 DWR chemistry has historically incorporated both sulfonyl based and telomer based chemistry but since the ban of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), what is denoted C8 DWR chemistry is commonly a telomer based (meth)acrylate product (note that also perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and PFOA related substances are since 2019 regulated by the Stockholm convention). Likewise, the C6 is also a telomer based system due to the bioaccumulation of the six carbon sulfonyl that made it irrelevant as a C8 replacer. C4 is commonly a sulfonyl-based chemistry.

The fluorochemical based DWR can be monomeric or polymeric but in modern DWR systems polymers are generally applied as those systems have better wash fastness and thus durability (Kissa 2001). According to Kissa (2001) most of those polymers are vinyl acrylic or methacrylic polymers. However, alternative application techniques, e.g. the addition of the perfluorinated monomer to the fiber polymer melt or co-polymerization with the fiber polymer, or application to performed fibers, are gaining interest also commercially (Kissa 2001).

The polymeric dispersions contain, in general, 80% water, 20% polymer and 0.5% impurities (Heydebreck *et al.* 2016). However, the industry of side-chain fluorinated polymers is currently going through a transition due to the recognition of the hazardousness of highly persistent PFAS (Wang *et al.* 2014). Part of this transition is a large reduction of the level of impurities in commercial products, which are believed to be reduced drastically after 2015. Wang *et al.* (2014) assumed the level of unreacted components in fluorotelomer based polymer products, after 2015, to be 0.000005-0.2% and to be mainly composed of FTOHs (Table S60 in (Wang *et al.* 2014)). Furthermore, Wang *et al.* (2014) assumed the content of impurities (remember that Wang differentiates between residuals and impurities) to consist mainly of PFHxA for a 6:2 based product, and to be negligible (0.00005%).

S4.2.1 C4 DWR

The C4 DWR was assumed to be based on side chain fluorinated polymers where the fluorinated side chain is a perfluorinated sulfonyl amide chemical intermediate (N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido alcohol). In the absence of the exact chemical structure a Backbone-C(CH₃)-C(O)O-CH₂CH₂-N(CH₃)-SO₂-C₄F₉ structure was assumed, as depicted in fig. S3 in (Holmquist *et al.* 2016). Furthermore, co-polymer alternatives were disregarded due to lack of information of the specific composition. Impurities in the form of unreacted or partially reacted starting material of 1-2% can be expected for PFOS based products (OECD 2002), and these numbers were assumed to be relevant also for perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS) based products (assumed to be weight-%), though acknowledged to likely be worst case as recent work has reduced the amount of impurities. Air emissions of impurities can be relevant as some of the PFBS precursors are semi-volatile (Król *et al.* 2011), but unaccounted for here as all impurities were estimated as PFBS.

The C4 DWR (mixture) was thus modelled to contain, in addition to water (wet weights were assumed if no other information was stated):

Table S3 Generic C4 DWR content based on collation of information sources as described above

Name	Content (%)
Water repellent	21-23
Impurity; perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS)	1-2% of side chain fluorinated polymer
Cosolvent	6-7
Dispersing agent	2-3

The LCI for the C4 DWR was modelled according to Table S4, based on relevant assumptions and proxies available in LCA databases. The N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer production was modelled according to S4.2.1.1 below. The vinyl polymer was assumed to be based on 2-(Methyl((nonafluorobutyl)sulfonyl)amino)ethylacrylate (CAS nr 67584-55-8), see e.g. Nielsen (2017). The cosolvent was modelled as ethylene glycol. Input of the dispersing agent was modelled as fatty acid while emissions were modelled as oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether (CAS 37251-67-5). Energy requirements were modelled according to S4.1. Chemical emissions were modelled according to the emission scenarios for chemical industry.

Table S4 LCI of the C4 DWR

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Ethylene glycol, at plant/RER	0.07	kg	
N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer	0.2	kg	
Fatty acids, from vegetarian oil, at plant/RER	0.03	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Heat, natural gas, at industrial furnace >100kW/RER	0.3	kWh	Modelled according to description in S4.1
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/RER	0.08	kWh	
Light fuel oil, burned in industrial furnace 1MW, non-modulating/RER	0.008	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	0.7	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
DWR FC-C4	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
Ethylene glycol	0.0007	kg	
Oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether	0.0003	kg	
PFBS	0.0006	kg	
Emissions to air			
Ethylene glycol	0.001	kg	
Oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether	0.0006	kg	
PFBS	0.001	kg	
Emissions to soil			
Ethylene glycol	0.0006	kg	
Oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether	0.0003	kg	
PFBS	0.0005	kg	

S4.2.1.1 N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer production

The manufacturing process for the perfluorinated compound was assumed to be ECF, by the Simons process as that is the one patented by 3M (Banks *et al.* 1994). In this process fluorination of organic molecules, dissolved in anhydrous hydrogen fluoride (AHF), is achieved by substitution at the anode of an electrochemical cell. The heavy fluorinated products are not soluble in the electrolyte and are collected at bottom of the cell. To increase the conductivity of the AHF organic or inorganic additives may need to be added (Kissa 2001). The yields span between 12-79% depending on alkane chain length (Kissa 2001). Based a yield of 79% for C2, 25% for C8 and 12% for C10 the yield was regressed on the number of carbons in the alkyl chain resulting in $y = -8.5192x + 95.462$ ($R^2 = 0.99$) and C4 yield was estimated as 61%. By-products are shorter chain sulfonyl fluorides or chlorides and fluorocarbons (Kissa 2001).

N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer is produced in a sequence to steps (based on Kissa (2001), here in unbalanced formulae):

1. Hydrofluoric acid (HF) is produced by reaction of calcium fluoride with sulfuric acid. The HF can contain several different impurities, e.g. fluorosulfonic acid (Kissa 2001).

2. The perfluorinated sulfonyl is produced with the ECF process.

3. The sulfonamide is produced by the addition of secondary amines.
4. The perfluorinated sulfonamides reacts in a similar way as their hydrocarbon analogues. The (meth)acrylate perfluorinated monomer is produced by addition of methyl(meth)acrylate. Here the methyl methacrylate (MMA) was assumed for the further modelling, using data from Plastic Europe (CEFIC 2014).
5. Finally, an aqueous latex is polymerized by copolymerization of the MMA monomer and one or several different non-fluorinated monomers. Besides the perfluorinated side chain and the different co-polymer units, the final polymer contains fiber reactive groups, see Holmquist *et al.* (2016).

Lacking more specific data the LCI for the N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer production was estimated by combination of database LCI data for the components of the polymer. The polymer was simplified to one MMA unit and one perfluorinated amide acrylate unit, i.e. a co-polymer with every other MMA being replaced with a perfluorinated amide unit. This simple co-polymer has a higher fluorine content than what can be assumed of most commercially available products. The databases did not contain the exact components used in the polymer manufacture and instead proxies were used, see Table S5. Instead of LCI data for the manufacture of perfluoro-1-butanesulfonyl fluoride, LCI data for sulfuric acid, hydrofluoric acid and butane were included in the model, and instead of LCI data for 3-(methylamino)propanoic acid, pentane was used. These were the closest analogues, based on structure, that were found in the databases. The required amounts of the chemicals were calculated on a stoichiometric basis (i.e. the number of moles required for 1 kg of the vinyl polymer and their respective weights). Data were not available on energy requirements. PFBS emissions were included according to the chemical industry emission scenario.

Table S5 LCI for manufacture of 1 kg N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer in the LCI model. Adjusted for a 61% yield of the main product.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Hydrogen fluoride	0.7	kg	
Methyl methacrylate (MMA)	0.3	kg	
Butanes from butenes, at plant/RER	0.2	kg	Proxy for Butanesulfonyl chloride (CAS 2386-60-9)
Pentane, at plant/RER	0.4	kg	Proxy for 3-(methylamino)propanoic acid (CAS 2679-14-3)
Sulphuric acid, liquid, at plant/RER	0.4	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
N-methyl perfluorobutanesulfonamido vinyl polymer	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
PFBS	0.003	kg	
Emissions to air			
PFBS	0.005	kg	
Emissions to soil			
PFBS	0.002	kg	

S4.2.2 C6 DWR

The water repellent component of the product was assumed to be a vinyl 6:2 fluorotelomer (meth)acrylate (6:2 FT(M)AC) polymer. The assumption was based on the fact that the C6 relevant commercial product described by the Fluoro Council (ENVIRON International Corporation 2014) was a methacrylate polymer and that Kissa (2001) describe the common fluoropolymer repellents as “vinyl polymers of acrylic or methacrylic type”. The Fluoro Council product was described as “Backbone-C(CH₃)-C(O)O-X-C_nF_{2n+1} where X is either -CH₂CH₂N(R')SO₂- with R' = -C_nH_{2n+1} (n=0,1,2,4) or -CH₂CH₂-“ (ENVIRON International Corporation 2014). In the absence of the exact chemical structure the Backbone-C(CH₃)-C(O)O-CH₂CH₂-C_nF_{2n+1} structure was assumed, as depicted in fig. 1 in Holmquist *et al.* (2016). The 6:2 FT(M)AC vinyl polymer can be expected to contain a number of PFAS impurities, with different characteristics. Herein all impurities were approximated as PFHxA or 6:2 FTOH based on Wang *et al.* (2014). Kissa (2001) state that the fluoroacrylate polymer content in a DWR product is within the 2-3% range. Russell *et al.* (2008) on the other hand report 24-28% fluoroacrylate polymer content in the DWR product they were testing and Heydebreck *et al.* (2016) state 20%. As the higher range, 24-28%, is stated in a later reference, that was the data used in the further modelling.

The C6 DWR (mixture), post-2015, was thus modelled to contain, in addition to water (wet weights were assumed if no other information was stated):

Table S6 Generic C6 DWR content based on collation of information sources as described above

Name	Content (%)
Water repellent	24-28
Impurity, 6:2 fluorotelomer alcohol (6:2 FTOH)	0.0005-0.2% of the fluorotelomer-based polymer
Impurity, perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	0.00005% of the fluorotelomer-based polymer
Cosolvent	3-7
Cosolvent (high volatility)	5-10
Dispersing agent	1-5

The LCI for the C6 DWR was modelled according to Table S7, based on relevant assumptions and proxies available in LCA databases. The 6:2 FT(M)AC was modelled using the Thinkstep (Sphera) dataset US: C-6 fluorinated acrylic copolymer (aggregated), which requires an additional curing step for polymerization (the curing is included later in the life cycle, in the DWR finishing process). Despite that the polymerization takes place in the finishing the 6:2 FT(M)AC was treated as a polymer with regards to emission scenarios. The cosolvent was modelled as ethylene glycol and the high volatility cosolvent was modelled as acetone. The dispersing agent was modelled as ethoxylated alcohols for input and poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -(1-oxooctadecyl)- ω -hydroxy- for emissions. Fluorotelomer alcohol (FTOH) content was modelled as 0.1% of the side-chain fluorinated polymer. Energy requirements were modelled according to S4.1. Emissions were modelled according to the chemical industry emission scenarios.

Table S7LCI for the C6 DWR

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
2-(Perfluorohexyl)ethyl acrylate	0.3	kg	Thinkstep (Sphera) process CAS: 17527-29-6
Acetone, liquid, at plant/RER	0.08	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols, unspecified, at plant/RER	0.03	kg	
Ethylene glycol, at plant/RER	0.06	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Heat, natural gas, at industrial furnace >100kW/RER	0.3		Modelled according to S4.1
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/RER	0.08		
Light fuel oil, burned in industrial furnace 1MW, non-modulating/RER	0.008		
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	0.6	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
DWR FC-C6 FTA based (post2015)	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
Acetone	0.0008	kg	
Ethylene Glycol	0.0006	kg	
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	0.0007	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -(1-oxooctadecyl)- ω -	0.0003	kg	
Emissions to air			
Acetone	0.002	kg	
Ethylene Glycol	0.001	kg	
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	3E-6	kg	
Emissions to soil			
Acetone	0.0008	kg	
Ethylene Glycol	0.0005	kg	
Perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA)	0.0006	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -(1-oxooctadecyl)- ω -	0.0003	kg	

S4.2.2.1 6:2 FTAC vinyl polymer production

The 6:2 FTAC vinyl polymer is produced in a sequence of steps. Below is a general description based on Banks *et al.* (1994) (formulae not balanced):

1. Perfluoroethyl iodide is produced by a reaction between iodine pentafluoride, iodine and tetrafluoroethylene. This step is carried out in liquid phase under pressure and in the presence of a catalyst (strong Lewis acids, e.g. antimony, tantalum or pentafluoride).

2. Longer chain perfluoroalkyl iodides (Telomer A, with even carbon numbers) are produced by telomerization of perfluoroethyl iodide with tetrafluoroethylene at elevated temperatures (or at lower temperatures in the presence of copper). This step can be carried out in either liquid (radical initiation) or vapor phase (thermal initiation, which will generate a mix of telomers n= 1 to 7). This is an exothermic reaction ($\Delta H = 192 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) typically carried out under positive pressure. It requires large excess of solvent or the starting iodide as a heat-transfer medium and the shorter chain iodides (C2-4) are re-used by

distillation. Other undesired by-products are removed by distillation. The end product has a composition with different distribution of telomer chain length depending on the proportion of reactants and heat-transfer medium.

3. Beta-(perfluoroalkyl)ethyl iodides (Telomer B) are produced by ethylation of the perfluoroalkyl iodide. The CF_2 -I bond is easily cleaved and ethylene is added by thermal insertion.

4. Beta-(perfluoroalkyl)ethyl iodides are further reacted to fluorotelomer alcohols and this can be done with several different reagents.

5. The fluorotelomer alcohols reacts in a similar way as they hydrocarbon analogues. The acrylate perfluorinated monomer is produced esterification with acrylic acid.
6. Finally, an aqueous latex is polymerized by copolymerization of the perfluoroalkylethyl acrylate monomer and one or several different non-fluorinated monomers.

The 2-(Perfluorohexyl)ethyl acrylate in the Thinkstep (Sphera) process included above (Table S7) is manufactured in processes following a similar reaction scheme as above.

Emissions of relevant perfluorinated substances were added to the model, based on (Wang *et al.* 2014), and the chemical industry emission scenario.

S4.2.3 C8 DWR

The C8 DWR was assumed to be identical to the C6 but with eight/seven carbon perfluorinated chains in the polymer side chains and impurities.

S4.3 DWRs based on hyperbranched polymers

The hyperbranched structures form three-dimensional surface enlargement structures that improve water repellency by arrangement of the water repellent moiety and the resemblance to wax surfaces on plant leaves. The DWRs based on hyperbranched polymers were assumed to consist of a hyperbranched structure (an alkylmodified polyurethane (PUR)) and a so-called comb polymer. Furthermore, the DWR chemical product was assumed to contain glycols and cationic and non-ionic surfactants. One kg of the DWR (mixture) was thus modelled to contain, in addition to water (wet weights were assumed if no other information was stated):

Table S8 Generic content of the DWR based on hyperbranched polymers, based on collation of information sources as described above

Name	Content (%)
Water repellent, functionalized polymer (hyperbranched)	5-15
Cosolvent	1-5
Dispersing agent, cationic surfactants	0.5-1
Dispersing agent, non-ionic surfactants	0.2-0.5

The LCI for the DWR was modelled according to Table S9, based on relevant assumptions and proxies available in LCA databases. The glycols were modelled as ethylene glycol and the unspecified surfactants were both modelled as fatty acids, from vegetarian oil, in the absence of more relevant processes. Emissions of the surfactants were modelled with Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl) , .alpha.-tridecyl-.omega.-hydroxy-, phosphate (CAS 9046-01-9), which was the surfactant with the best data quality of the surfactants with characterization factors calculated by Roos *et al.* (2018). Emissions were applied according to the chemical industry emission scenarios.

Table S9 LCI for the DWR based on hyperbranched polymers

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Ethylene glycol	0.03	kg	
Fatty acids, from vegetarian oil, at plant/RER	0.01	kg	
Functionalized polymer	0.08	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Heat, natural gas, at industrial furnace >100kW/RER	0.3	kWh	See S4.1
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/RER	0.08	kWh	
Light fuel oil, burned in industrial furnace 1MW, non-modulating/RER	0.008	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	0.97	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
DWR hyperbranched	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
Ethylene glycol	0.0003	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl) , .alpha.-tridecyl-.omega.-hydroxy-, phosphate	0.0001	kg	
Emissions to air			
Ethylene glycol	0.0007	kg	
Emissions to soil			
Ethylene glycol	0.0003	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl) , .alpha.-tridecyl-.omega.-hydroxy-, phosphate	0.0001	kg	

S4.3.1.1 Hyperbranched functionalized polymer

The functionalized polymer was modelled using database data to represent the three chemical components; PUR as the hyperbranched structure (modelled with ECOINVENT process RER: polyurethane, flexible foam, at plant.), paraffin wax as the water repellent moiety (modelled with GaBi TS process EU-28: Wax / Paraffins at refinery ts) and an organic chemical as the comb polymer. Mass fraction of the respective components were arbitrarily set to 0.9, 0.05 and 0.05, respectively, since the water repellent moiety and the comb polymer probably make up a small part of the total structure of the functionalized polymer. The calculated theoretical energy consumption for manufacturing the hyperbranched polymer was assumed to be <0.5 kWh/kg.

S4.4 Hydrocarbon based DWRs

There are two types of wax products used for DWR; hard wax and wax emulsion. Even though the water repellent moiety in both cases is a hydrocarbon alkyl chain, see Holmquist *et al.* (2016) Fig. 1, the full molecular structure as well as finishing technique is very different. In the modelling herein wax emulsion was considered a relevant product, selected for modelling.

S4.4.1 Wax (emulsion) DWR

Wax emulsion DWR products have different chemical compositions; metal salts, melamine based and acrylate co-polymers (Holmquist *et al.* 2016). The metal salts do not need curing (European Commission 2003 p. 506) but the more modern acrylate products are used in DWR finishing by application of the standard pad-dry-cure process. Copolymerisate of acrylates represent a modern wax emulsion product and was selected for the further modelling. To achieve crystallization of the side chains 8-12 carbons are needed in the alkyl chain (Greenberg and Alfrey 1954; (Holmquist *et al.* 2016)). Common chain lengths are likely C15-C17. The alkyl hydrocarbon chain originates from paraffin wax. Paraffin wax is a petroleum product consisting of straight chain hydrocarbons, generally 20-40 carbons and longer (PothHille 2020). In addition to the functional polymer and water, emulsifiers (dispersing agents) and possibly also cosolvents are probably contained in the product.

The wax emulsion DWR formulation was thus modelled to contain, in addition to water (wet weights were assumed if no other information was stated):

Table S10 Generic wax (polymer emulsion) DWR content based on collation of information sources as described above

Name	Content (%)
Water repellent	20-30
Cosolvent	0.1-10
Dispersing agent	0.1-5

The wax DWR (emulsion) was modelled according to Table S11, based on relevant assumptions and proxies available in LCA databases. The manufacture of the wax emulsions was modelled as ELCD/TS Wax / Paraffins at refinery (EU-28) and Methyl methacrylate (MMA), in a 1:2 ratio. The cosolvent was assumed to be alcohols, C 12-13,ethoxylated. The dispersing agent was assumed to be cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride, modelled using the

hexamethylene diamine (HMDA) (see Section S4.5.1). Emission scenarios for chemical industry were applied. Emissions of the co-polymerizate was modelled to generate emissions of paraffins as a degradation product (Holmquist *et al.* 2016).

Table S11 LCI of the HC-Wax (emulsion) DWR

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Copolymerisate of acrylates (HC)	0.3	kg	
Hexamethylene diamine (HMDA)	0.03	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols, unspecified, at plant/RER	0.06	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Heat, natural gas, at industrial furnace >100kW/RER	0.3	kWh	Modelled according to S4.1
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/RER	0.08	kWh	
Light fuel oil, burned in industrial furnace 1MW, non-modulating/RER	0.008	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	0.7	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
DWR HC-Wax (emulsion)	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
Cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride	0.0003	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -(1-oxooctadecyl)- ω -	0.0006	kg	
Paraffins	0.0009	kg	
Emissions to soil			
Cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride	0.0003	kg	
Poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -(1-oxooctadecyl)- ω -	0.0005	kg	
Paraffins	0.0008	kg	

S4.5 Silicone based DWRs

Silicone based DWR provide the water repellent function with a cross linked network formed on the fabric. The basic structure for this network is Si-O-Si, with additional groups providing the cross-linking capability. The exact chemical being the basis for this cross-linking differ between products. It is also generally considered a business secret. The structure was approximated with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (Holmquist *et al.* 2016). Silicone based DWRs can contain cyclic siloxanes as impurities. Degradation products considered relevant were short-chain silanols, DMSD and TMS (Holmquist *et al.* 2016).

S4.5.1 Silicon DWR

The silicone based DWR was based on products for which no additional auxiliary chemicals such as crosslinkers and catalyst are needed. According to Brooke *et al.* (2009), (2009) the cyclic siloxanes D4 and D5 can be contained as impurities in PDMS based polymers in the ranges of 430-3360 and 570-3110 ppm, respectively. In the modern silicone systems, the content of these impurities has been possible to reduce to zero for some systems (pers. comm. van der Veen) or to total concentrations of approximately 500 ppm.

The silicone DWR formulation was thus modelled to contain, in addition to water (wet weights were assumed if no other information was stated):

Table S12 Generic Si DWR content, based on collation of information sources as described above

Name	Content (%)
Water repellent	20-30
Cosolvent (high volatility)	1-3
Cosolvent	0.3-1
Dispersing agent	0.1-0.3
Impurity, octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane, D4	500 or 0 ppm of PDMS
Impurity, decamethylcyclopentasiloxane, D5	
Impurity, DMSD	1% of PDMS
Impurity, TMS	0.01% of PDMS

The Si DWR was modelled according to Table S13, based on relevant assumptions and proxies available in LCA databases. The PDMS was modelled with the Thinkstep (Sphera) process data set: Silicone fluids (highly viscous) / polydimethylsiloxanes (from organosilanes); from organosilanes; single route, at plant; highly viscous (en). The output from this silicone process was a flow of Silicone fluids (very viscous), not specified by CAS number. Furthermore, the silicone dataset did not include emissions of D4, D5, TMS or DMSD and their emissions were added separately, using the chemical industry emission scenario. According to Graiver *et al.* (2003) the main part of the PDMS is transformed to DMSD and thus all PDMS emissions were converted to DMSD. No stoichiometric calculations were made but the full amount of PDMS, in weight, was assumed to generate the same weight of DMSD. Nitrogen containing substances were assumed to be active as dispersing agents and/or catalysts/crosslinkers. The GaBi process DE: Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA; via adipic acid) was used to model the input of nitrogen containing compounds. For emissions ionic nitrogen compounds were approximated with cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride and non-ionic were approximated with hexadecyldimethylamine. The high volatility cosolvents were approximated with ethanol and methanol. Further input of dispersing agent was modelled as fatty alcohol and emissions as alcohols, C12-14, ethoxylated (CAS 68439-50-9). The chemical industry emission scenarios were applied to calculate emissions.

Table S13 LCI for the Si DWR

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Hexamethylene diamine (HMDA)	0.006	kg	
Methanol, at plant/GLO	0.006	kg	
Fatty alcohol, petrochemical, at plant/RER	0.007	kg	
Ethanol from ethylene, at plant/RER	0.02	kg	
Silicone fluids (very viscous)	0.3	kg	DE: Silicone fluids (highly viscous) / polydimethylsiloxanes (from organosilanes) ts
Electricity/heat			
Heat, natural gas, at industrial furnace >100kW/RER	0.3	kWh	See S4.1
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/RER	0.08	kWh	
Light fuel oil, burned in industrial furnace 1MW, non-modulating/RER	0.008	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	0.8	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
DWR Si-PDMS based (incl. cyclic siloxanes)	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
Alcohols, C12-14, ethoxylated	7E-05	kg	
Cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride	4E-05	kg	
D4, Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane	7E-07	kg	
D5, Decamethylcyclopentasiloxane	7E-07	kg	
Dimethylsilanediol (DMSD)	0.003	kg	
Ethanol	0.0002	kg	
Hexadecyldimethylamine	0.00002	kg	
Hydroxytrimethylsilane (trimethylsilanol) (TMS)	3E-07	kg	
Methanol	6E-05	kg	
Emissions to air			
D4, Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane	1E-06	kg	
D5, Decamethylcyclopentasiloxane	1E-06	kg	
Dimethylsilanediol (DMSD)	0.006	kg	
Ethanol	0.0004	kg	
Hydroxytrimethylsilane (trimethylsilanol) (TMS)	6E-7	kg	
Methanol	0.0001	kg	
Emissions to soil			
Alcohols, C12-14, ethoxylated	6E-05	kg	
Cetyltrimethyl ammonium chloride	4E-05	kg	
D4, Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane	6E-07	kg	
D5, Decamethylcyclopentasiloxane	6E-07	kg	
Dimethylsilanediol (DMSD)	0.003	kg	
Ethanol	0.0002	kg	
Hexadecyldimethylamine	2E-05	kg	
Hydroxytrimethylsilane (trimethylsilanol) (TMS)	3E-07	kg	
Methanol	6E-05	kg	

S4.6 Auxiliary chemicals in finishing

S4.6.1 Crosslinker/booster

The crosslinker or booster is often a blocked isocyanate. Available LCI dataset are methylene diphenyl diisocyanate, at plant, and toluene diisocyanate, at plant. They have different environmental performance and the methylene diphenyl diisocyanate has higher (eco)toxicity impacts. However, the toluene diisocyanate is characterized in GaBi with USEtox CFs and was selected for further modelling. Active ingredient has been stated to be in 20-30% in a water solution in some cross-linker products. The 20-30% range was used in the further modelling. Some of the crosslinker products have solvents, dispersion agents and biocides included as well. These were not further regarded.

S4.6.2 Catalyst

Catalysts may be needed with silicone systems. The catalysts are used because the curing temperatures needed in silicone systems are too high for textiles and catalysts are necessary to reduce temperature (Kissa 2001). Silicone based system catalysts aid the film forming and proper orientation of the silicone polymer, e.g. by affecting sorption and orientation of the polymer (Kissa 2001). The catalyst increases the durability of the hydrophobicity by increasing the cross-linking (Lenoble 2009). The term catalyst is probably used with somewhat different meanings when the silicone systems are described. In any case, a silicone based DWR need auxiliary chemicals to catalyze reactions in order to decrease curing temperatures, and to crosslink the silicone polymer to the fabric fibers. Instead of modelling the catalyst separately a product not needing further catalyst was modelled for the Si-system, see S4.5.1.

S4.6.3 Biocides

DWR products can contain biocides. Biocides were not included in the DWR models.

S4.6.4 Wetting agents

Wetting agents are often used in DWR finishing and can be for example fatty alcohol ethoxylates, i.e. similar to the dispersing agent. This was not further considered in the modelling.

S4.7 Finishing

For all DWR systems a water-based padding finishing was assumed. The padding is followed by drying and curing. The finishing process for each DWR system is described below after a general overview.

Conventionally the DWR is applied to the fabric by a wet treatment process where the fabric is dipped in the DWR containing solution, padded in foulards and dried (120-180 °C) and cured (1-3 min, 150-182 °C) (Kissa 2001). The normal pick-up rate in foulard application is 70% but there are so called minimum application systems available, reducing the pick-up to 30% (European Commission 2003). Normal rates for system losses are 1-5% (European Commission 2003). Industrial contacts estimated data for pick-up to 30-80% and losses to be in the lower range of 1-5% for the fluorine containing DWRs, for which left overs are sent to destruction, and probably higher for the non-fluorinated alternatives as those do not have to be sent for destruction.

S4.7.1 DWR consumption and emissions

The DWR consumption will be determined by many different factors, maybe most important the content of functional polymer (i.e. the water repellent active ingredient). Herein, the amount of DWR formulation used for each DWR was back-calculated based on the content of the water repellent chemical in the formulation and the content of the water repellent chemical on the garment. The calculation is described in Eq. 1-2, where DWR_{USE} is the amount (kg) of DWR formulation used per kg textile treated, $DWR_{USE+LOSS}$, is the total DWR used including waste, f_{WR} is the fraction of water repellent chemical in the DWR formulation, f_{WR-G} is the fraction of water repellent chemical on the textile, and f_{LOSS} is the system loss (5% in basic scenario).

$$\text{Eq. 1: } DWR_{USE} = f_{WR-G} / f_{WR}$$

$$\text{Eq. 2: } DWR_{USE+LOSS} = DWR_{USE} / (1 - f_{LOSS})$$

Textile finishing emission scenarios were applied to system losses for the property lending chemical and to the full amount for all auxiliaries.

S4.7.2 Energy requirements and water use

Energy requirements for finishing as listed in the BREF (European Commission 2003), see Table S14, was re-calculated to a per kg textile basis for the further use in the LCA model (1000 m fabric = 100 kg). In the BREF a washing step is included but was not included in the present model as the fabric was assumed to be dried after the dyeing process and sent straight to the stenter for finishing. Energy use for the preceding processes, from raw material storage to dyeing and subsequent drying, was included (on another data basis) in the inventories for the PA and polyester (PES) fabrics. As part of LCI work herein offers specifying a new stenter were used (BREF data only used for comparison with regards to energy requirements). The average values from the 3.6 m stenter specification were used in the further modelling of energy requirements and the water consumption was taken from the BREF (finishing step).

Table S14 Average data from specifications for a 3.6 m stenter and BREF (fig. 3.10 “Analysis of thermal and electric energy consumption for the finishing of viscose/PES fabric”. Energy consumption values re-calculated from 1000 m fabric length, 1.4 m fabric width, specific weight ca 100 g/m and steam 3 bar, ca 133°C. Data originally published in 2000.)

Process	3.6 m wide stenter, per kg fabric	BREF per kg fabric
Washing		0.051 kWh _{elec} 2.02 kg _{steam} 0.009 m ³ water
Finishing and drying (stenter)	0.25 kWh _{elec} 1.9 kWh _{gas}	0.14 kWh _{elec} 2.26 kWh _{gas} 0.69 kg _{steam} 0.001 m ³ water
Calendering		0.058 kWh _{elec}
Final control		0.026 kWh _{elec}

S4.7.3 Use of auxiliary textile chemicals

The present study cannot capture all possible scenarios and a generic finishing recipe was set up. The model was set up identical for all side-chain fluorinated polymer DWR systems, disregarding that the C8 may have less need for crosslinkers. The use of extenders was not included in the model. The crosslinker weight on the fabric was set to 50% of DWR functional polymer weight and consumption was calculated using Eq 1-2 above. The textile processing emission scenario was applied to calculate emissions. No catalyst was included for the Si-DWR (see Section S4.5.1).

S4.7.4 Side-chain fluorinated polymer DWR finishing

Finishing amounts were calculated with the back-calculation approach (Eq.1-2). Banks *et al.* (1994) state that a DWR treated fabric contain 0.05-0.5% DWR. based on recent measurements, herein 1% deposited polymer (weight fraction on textile, (Schellenberger *et al.* 2019)) was used together with the respective polymer content in the DWR-formulation, depending on DWR chemistry. The textile processing emission scenario was applied to calculate emissions.

S4.7.5 Si DWR finishing

Finishing amounts were calculated with the back-calculation approach (Eq.1-2). The final fabric was assumed to contain 1-2% DWR (Kissa 2001). 1.5% deposited polymer (weight fraction on textile) was used together with the content of silicone emulsion in the DWR-formulation. The textile processing emission scenario was applied to calculate emissions.

S4.7.6 Wax (emulsion) DWR finishing

Finishing amounts were calculated with the back-calculation approach (Eq.1-2). Finishing with wax emulsions is sensitive to residues on the fabric or from other finishing treatments (Lang, Idstein 2014), but no extra washing step was included. We assumed that deposited polymer does not deviate from the Si-system. A 1.5% was used in the modelling. The textile processing emission scenario was applied to calculate emissions.

S4.7.7 Hyperbranched polymers, DWR finishing

Finishing amounts were calculated with the back-calculation approach (Eq.1-2). Polymer deposition on the fabric was set to 0.7% of fabric weight. The textile processing emission scenario was applied to calculate emissions.

S4.8 Synthetic weaves

PES and PA weaves were modelled based on previous models published by Roos *et al.* (2019). Background data were taken from ecoinvent 2.2 (as implemented in GaBi). The modelling was kept as general as possible to allow for inclusion of these processes in the models of different outdoor garments. The general process flowchart, applicable to both PES and PA manufacture, is shown in Figure S2.

Figure S2 General system description for the manufacture of polyamide and polyester weaves.

The PES and PA weaves were modelled as similarly as possible and the LCI per process is described below.

S4.8.1 Electricity mix

The electricity was modelled with the weighted electricity mix put together by Roos *et al.* (2015; A2.1.1.1); combining Chinese (65%), Bangladesh (23%) and Turkish electricity (12%). ecoinvent 2.2 datasets, according to Roos *et al.* (2015; A2.1.1.2, A2.1.1.3) were used for the electricity datasets making up the mix. This is the electricity mix used by Roos *et al.* (2016), (2019) in their LCAs on textile value chains.

S4.8.2 PES weave

S4.8.2.1 Polymer production

Manufacture of the polyester polymer was modelled with the dataset "RER: polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous, at plant" (agg) in the ecoinvent 2.2 database (GaBi version). This dataset contains data for the polyethylene terephthalate (PET) production out of purified terephthalic acid (PTA) and ethylene glycol based on data from several European production sites.

S4.8.2.2 Melt spinning to fibers

PES melt spinning to filament fibers was modelled based on process 2 in Roos *et al.* (2019): Melt spinning of PES to fibres, average (mix), see Table S15.

Table S15 LCI for the melt spinning to 1 kg of PES fibers, based on Roos *et al.* (2019). Upstream processes from ecoinvent 2.2.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous, at plant [polymers]/RER	1	kg	
Lubricating oil, at plant/RER	0.01	kg	
Manganese, at regional storage/RER	0.0002	kg	Accelerator
Antimony, at refinery/CN	0.0002	kg	Catalyst
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	1.5	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1
Heat, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW, non-modulating/CH S	2.2	MJ	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PES filament fibres	1	kg	
Emissions to air			
Terephthalate, dimethyl	0.00001	kg	Monomer/oligomer

S4.8.2.3 Spinning to yarn

Spinning to yarn was modelled based on process 10 in Roos et al. (2019): Filament DTY yarn production, 100 dtex , average (mix), see Table S16.

Table S16 LCI for the yarn spinning of 1 kg PES filament yarn, based on Roos et al. (2019). Upstream processes fromecoinvent 2.2.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
PES filament fibers	1.01	kg	
Lubricating oil, at plant/RER	0.0305	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	2.08	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1
Compressed air, average generation, >30kW, 6 bar gauge, at compressor/RER S	25	m3	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PES yarn	1	kg	
Emissions to air			
Acrylamide	9.2E-08	kg	Breakdown product
Formaldehyde	9.2E-09	kg	Breakdown product
Waste to treatment			
Waste incineration of textile fraction in municipal solid waste (MSW)	0.005	kg	

S4.8.2.4 Weaving

Weaving was modelled based on process 13 in Roos et al. (2019): Weaving, 150 dtex, average (mix), see Table S17.

Table S17 LCI for the weaving of 1 kg PES weave, based on Roos et al. (2019). Upstream processes fromecoinvent 2.2.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
PES yarn	1.01	kg	
Lubricating oil, at plant/RER	0.0305	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	9.87	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PES fabric	1	kg	
Waste to treatment			
Waste incineration of textile fraction in municipal solid waste (MSW)	0.005	kg	

S4.8.2.5 Dyeing weave

Dyeing was modelled based on process 23 in Roos *et al.* (2019): Dyeing PES weave orange in beam dyeing machine, average (mix), see Table S18.

Table S18 LCI for the dyeing of 1 kg PES weave, based on data from Roos *et al.* (2019). Upstream processes fromecoinvent 2.2 unless otherwise annotated.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
PES fabric	1	kg	
Chemicals inorganic, at plant/GLO	0.08	kg	Sequestering agent, decalcifier, soda
Chemicals organic, at plant/GLO	0.2	kg	Yellow disperse dyestuff, red disperse dyestuff, softener
Ethoxylated alcohols (AE7), petrochemical, at plant/RER	0.2	kg	Detergent, wetting agent, dispersant,
Formic acid, at plant/RER	0.03	kg	
Hydrogen peroxide, 50% in H2O, at plant/RER	0.03	kg	
Silicone fluids (very viscous)	0.003	kg	Antifoaming agent, Thinkstep (Sphera)
Sodium hydroxide, 50% in H2O, production mix, at plant/RER	0.005	kg	
Sodium percarbonate, powder, at plant/RER	0.01	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	0.7	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1
Heat, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW condensing, non-modulating/CH	8.4	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	78	kg	7 baths, 1:10 ratio
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PES fabric	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
1,2-dihydro-6-hydroxy-1,4-dimethyl-2-oxo-5-[[3-[(phenylsulphonyloxy]phenyl]azo]nicotinonitrile	3.00E-06	kg	
2-(3-oxobenzo[b]thien-2(3H)-ylidene)benzo[b]thiophene-3(2H)-one	6.50E-05	kg	
2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	0.0003	kg	Iso-octyl alcohol
2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one	3.00E-07	kg	
5-chloro-2-methyl-4-isothiazoline-3-one	3.00E-07	kg	
Alcoholsulfate	3.00E-07	kg	Sodium lauryl sulphate
Ammonium sulphate	0.002	kg	
C9-11 Alcohol ethoxylate	0.0006	kg	
Calcium carbonate	0.002	kg	
COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand	0.0002	kg	
Diethanolamine	3.00E-05	kg	
Dimethyl siloxane, reaction product with silica	1.50E-05	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohol (NPEO)	0.00015	kg	
Ethylene oxide	1.50E-06	kg	
Fatty methylester sulfonates	0.0009	kg	
Formaldehyde	1.50E-07	kg	

Formic acid	0.003	kg	
Hydrogen peroxide	0.0003	kg	
Isotridecanol ethoxylated	0.002	kg	
Nonylphenol	1.50E-07	kg	
Octadecanoic acid	0.0002	kg	
Oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether	0.00425	kg	
Phosphonic acid, disodium salt	0.0012	kg	
Polyacrylic acid, sodium salt	0.001683	kg	
Sodium carbonate (Na ₂ CO ₃)	0.00051	kg	
Sodium disulfate	4.00E-05	kg	
Sodium dithionite	0.00045	kg	
Sodium hydroxide	0.000506	kg	
Sodium mono(2-ethylhexyl)estersulfate	0.00085	kg	
Thiosulfate	4.50E-07	kg	
Emissions to air			
1,2-dihydro-6-hydroxy-1,4-dimethyl-2-oxo-5-[[3-[(phenylsulphonyloxy]phenyl]azo]nicotinonitrile	6.00E-07	kg	
2-(3-oxobenzo[b]thien-2(3H)-ylidene)benzo[b]thiophene-3(2H)-one	1.30E-05	kg	
2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	3.00E-06	kg	Iso-octyl alcohol
C9-11 Alcohol ethoxylate	6.00E-06	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohol (NPEO)	1.50E-06	kg	
Ethylene oxide	1.50E-08	kg	
Formaldehyde	1.50E-08	kg	
Formic acid	3.00E-05	kg	
Hydrogen peroxide	3.00E-05	kg	
Isotridecanol ethoxylated	3.00E-06	kg	
Phosphonic acid, disodium salt	1.20E-05	kg	
Waste to treatment			
Disposal, sludge from pulp and paper production, 25% water, to sanitary landfill/CH	0.5	kg	

S4.8.2.6 *Drying weave*

Drying was modelled according to process 27 in Roos *et al.* (2019): Drying and fixation of synthetics, average (mix), see Table S19.

Table S19 LCI for the drying and fixation of 1 kg PES weave, data from Roos *et al.* (2019). Upstream processes from ecoinvent 2.2.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
PES fabric	1	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	0.8	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1.
Heat, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW, non-modulating/CH	2.2	kWh	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PES fabric	1	kg	

S4.8.3 *PA weave*

The PA fabric was modelled as the PES fabric with the exception that the starting material (the polymer) was nylon instead of polyethylene terephthalate and a PA specific dyeing process was used. The processes spinning to yarn, weaving and drying are therefore not further described here.

S4.8.3.1 *Nylon 6.6*

Manufacture of the polyamide polymer was modelled with the dataset "RER: nylon 66, at plant [Polymers]" (agg) in the ecoinvent 2.2 database (GaBi version). Nylon 6,6 is a polyamide polymer made of hexamethylene diamine and adipic acid.

S4.8.3.2 *Melt spinning to fibers*

PA melt spinning to filament fibers was modelled according to process 4 in Roos *et al.* (2019): Melt spinning of PA66 to fibres, average (mix), see Table S20.

Table S20 LCI for the melt spinning to 1 kg of PA fibers, data from Roos *et al.* (2019). Upstream processes fromecoinvent 2.2.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Nylon 66, at plant/RER	1	kg	
Lubricating oil, at plant/RER	0.01	kg	
Manganese, at regional storage/RER	0.0001	kg	Accelerator
Antimony, at refinery/CN	0.00005	kg	Catalyst
Cobalt, at plant/GLO S	0.00005	kg	Accelerator
Phosphoric acid, industrial grade, 85% in H ₂ O, at plant/RER	0.0001	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	1.5	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter S4.8.1.
Heat, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW, non-modulating/CH S	2.2	MJ	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PA 6.6 filament fibres	1	kg	
Emissions to air			
Adipic acid	1.0E-05	kg	
Adipic acid, compound with hexane-1,6-diamine (1:1)	1.0E-05	kg	
N,n'-dimethylacetamide	5.0E-07	kg	

S4.8.3.3 Dyeing weave

Dyeing was modelled based on process 22 in Roos *et al.* (2019): Dyeing PA6 weave black in beam dyeing machine, average (mix), see Table S21.

Table S21 LCI for the dyeing of 1 kg PA weave, data from Roos *et al.* (2019). Upstream processes fromecoinvent 2.2 unless otherwise annotated.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
PA fabric	1	kg	
Chemicals inorganic, at plant/GLO	0.05	kg	Sequestering agent, soda
Chemicals organic, at plant/GLO	0.06	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols (AE7), petrochemical, at plant/RER	0.1	kg	Detergent, wetting agent
Formic acid, at plant/RER	0.05	kg	
Lubricant (unspecified)	0.02	kg	
Silicone fluids (very viscous)	0.003	kg	Antifoaming agent
Sodium hydroxide, 50% in H ₂ O, production mix, at plant/RER	0.01	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	0.7	kWh	Modelled according to description in chapter 2
Heat, light fuel oil, at boiler 10kW condensing, non-modulating/CH	8.4	kWh	
Water			

Tap water, at user	88	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
PA fabric	1	kg	
Emissions to water			
2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	0.00018	kg	Iso-octyl alcohol
2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one	3.00E-07	kg	
5-chloro-2-methyl-4-isothiazoline-3-one	3.00E-07	kg	
Acrylamide	6.00E-07	kg	
Acrylamide/sodium acrylate copolymer	0.00059	kg	
Alcohols, C11-14-iso-, C13-rich	0.0015	kg	
Alcoholsulfate	3.00E-07	kg	Sodium lauryl sulphate
Calcium carbonate	0.001	kg	
COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand	0.0002	kg	
Dimethyl siloxane, reaction product with silica	1.50E-05	kg	
Diocetyl sodium sulfosuccinate	2.50E-06	kg	
Disperse Black 1	0.00019	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohol (NPEO)	9.00E-05	kg	
Ethylene oxide	1.00E-06	kg	
Fatty methylester sulfonates	0.00054	kg	
Formaldehyde	1.60E-07	kg	
Formic acid	0.005	kg	
Isotridecanol ethoxylated	0.001	kg	
Nonylphenol	9.00E-08	kg	
Oxirane, methyl-, polymer with oxirane, decyl ether	0.0025	kg	
Phosphonic acid, disodium salt	0.0012	kg	
Polyacrylic acid, sodium salt	0.00099	kg	
Reactive Blue 4	5.60E-06	kg	
Sodium carbonate (Na ₂ CO ₃)	0.001	kg	
Sodium hydroxide	6.00E-06	kg	
Sodium mono(2-ethylhexyl)estersulfate	0.0005	kg	
Emissions to air			
2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	1.80E-06	kg	Iso-octyl alcohol
Acrylamide	6.00E-08	kg	
Alcohols, C11-14-iso-,C13-rich	1.50E-05	kg	
Diocetyl sodium sulfosuccinate	5.00E-07	kg	
Disperse Black 1	3.80E-05	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohol (NPEO)	9.00E-07	kg	
Ethylene oxide	1.00E-08	kg	
Formaldehyde	1.60E-08	kg	
Formic acid	5.00E-05	kg	
Phosphonic acid, disodium salt	1.20E-05	kg	
Reactive Blue 4	1.10E-06	kg	
Waste to treatment			
Disposal, sludge from pulp and paper production, 25% water, to sanitary landfill /CH	0.5	kg	

S4.9 Standard jacket

S4.9.1 Bill of materials (BOM)

The bill of material (BOM) of a standard rain jacket was kindly shared by a producer of such a jacket. When information was missing proxy data were assigned based on experiences in the data collection for the other garments in the project. This BOM was simplified by aggregation of materials (Table S22). The outer fabric and waterproof coating are in fact one composite material. The DWR on the outer fabric is here unspecified as this jacket provide the basis for evaluation of several different DWRs in hypothetical scenarios.

In construction of the BOM it was assumed that material waste was 17% (based on Roos *et al.* (2019)) and that outer fabric weight (g/sqm) is for the coated fabric. The actual fabric losses in confectioning may be higher as the actual jacket weighted 240 g, i.e. 60 g less than material summation in the BOM.

Table S22 Bill of material standard rain jacket

Material name	Material type	Weight in jacket (g)
Outer fabric	PA6.6	109
Other fabric components	PES	4.6
Tapes	Acrylic	43
Zippers	PA6	32
Waterproof coating	PU	109
Labels	Silicone	6.2
Total		304
Packaging	LDPE plastic	30
Hangtags	Cardboard	10
Total		344

S4.9.2 Manufacturing

- The outer fabric was modelled with the PA fabric model (S4.8.3).
- The other fabric components, such as wash instruction labels, piping knits, zipper pulls etc., were modelled with the PES fabric model (S4.8.2).
- Tapes were assumed to be made of acrylic and were modelled with the ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version) dataset “RER: polymethyl methacrylate, sheet, at plant” (agg).
- No product specifications were available for the zippers in the jacket. In general terms they are composed of plastic (the “sawtooth” part), metal (the runner) and fabric (the backing of the sawtooth). In a very

simplified approach, the zippers were modelled as extrusion on nylon 6 with datasets from ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version). RER: nylon 6, at plant and RER: extrusion, plastic pipes.

- The PU membrane was modelled as RER: polyurethane, flexible foam, at plant with dataset from ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version).
- The logo-label was modelled as RER: silicone product, at plant with dataset from ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version).
- The plastic packaging was modelled as RER: packaging film, LDPE, at plant with dataset from ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version).
- Hangtags were modelled as RER: paper, recycling, with deinking, at plant with dataset from ecoinvent 2.2 (GaBi version).

S4.9.2.1 Confectioning

Confectioning was modelled with processes 28 Cutting, average (mix) and 29 Sewing, average (mix) in (Roos *et al.* 2019). The generation of confectioning waste was modelled only for the laminate. The confectioning was assumed to take in Asia and the weighted electricity mix (see S4.8.1) was used. No additional energy use was added for the labelling and packaging.

Table S23: LCI for the confectioning of one jacket.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Labels	0.0062	kg	
PA fabric	0.131	kg	
PES fabric	0.0046	kg	
PU water proof coating	0.131	kg	
Tape	0.043	kg	
Zippers	0.032	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity mix	0.218	kWh	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
Rain jacket standard	0.304	kg	
Confectioning waste	0.061	kg	EU-28: Waste incineration of textile fraction in municipal solid waste (MSW) ELCD/CEWEP

S4.9.2.2 *Transports*

All transports in the supply chain were aggregated into two types of transport:

- OCE: transport, transoceanic freight ship [Water], 7 tkm
- RER: transport, lorry 16-32t, EURO3 [Street], 0.3 tkm

These numbers were based on an inventory for another shell garment and are rough approximations.

S4.9.3 *Use phase*

Use phase diffuse emissions were calculated according to S3.2.

S4.9.3.1 *Unpacking*

The packaging materials were assumed to be sent to incineration (Table S24). Transport was modelled as 0.0002 tkm CH: transport, municipal waste collection, lorry 21t.

Table S24 LCI for the unpacking

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Rain jacket standard (in packaging)	0.344	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
Rain jacket standard	0.304	kg	
Waste to treatment			
Packaging waste (plastic)	0.03	kg	CH: disposal, plastics, mixture, 15.3% water, to municipal incineration
Waste incineration of paper fraction in municipal solid waste (MSW)	0.01	kg	CH: disposal, paper, 11.2% water, to municipal incineration

S4.9.3.2 *Washing and drying*

The washing and drying was modelled based on Roos *et al.* (2015) Tab. A2.3.2.1 and A2.3.3.1; wash at 40 degrees and drying in tumble dryer (Table S25). The jacket was assumed to be washed separately thus the data were scaled to the average for a full machine (3.6 kg), assuming that the user adjusts the detergent load and that the machine adjusts the water and electricity use. The wash water was modelled to be sent to a WWTP class 2. The jacket was assumed to be washed 9 times over its 5-year life length.

Table S25 LCI for the domestic washing and drying, one wash and dry cycle

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Domestic washing detergent	0.004	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity, low voltage, production SE, at grid/SE	0.27	kWh	
Water			
Tap water, at user/RER	1.9	kg	
Outputs			
Waste to treatment			
CH: treatment, sewage, from residence, to wastewater treatment, class 2 [wastewater treatment]	1.9	kg	

S4.9.3.3 Washing detergent

The detergent production was modelled based on table A2.3.1 in Roos *et al.* (2015), which in turn was based on Saouter and Hoof (2002). Manufacturing data for citric acid (5.2%) and the antifoaming agent (0.5%) (i.e. upstream data) were not available in ecoinvent 2.2. The detergent was modelled to have an output of 943 g despite the basis on a “1 kg recipe”, thus the ingredients with LCI upstream data were assumed to be representative also for citric acid and the antifoaming agent. The production was set to occur in Sweden. The disposal of packaging materials was modelled within the detergent production process.

Table S26 LCI for the production of 943 g domestic washing detergent.

	Amount	Unit	Comment
Inputs			
Material/fuels			
Corrugated board base paper, kraftliner, at plant/RER	0.106	kg	
DAS-1, fluorescent whitening agent triazinylaminostilben type, at plant/RER	0.002	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols (AE11), palm oil, at plant RER	0.02	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols (AE7), petrochemical, at plant/RER	0.04	kg	
Ethoxylated alcohols, unspecified, at plant (tensides)/RER	0.078	kg	
Kraft paper, unbleached, at plant/RER	0.0206	kg	
Polyacrylate granulate [Plastics]	0.04	kg	DE: Polymethylmethacrylate granulate (PMMA) ts
Polyethylene, HDPE, granulate, at plant/RER	0.0076	kg	
Sodium carbonate from ammonium chloride production, at plant/RER	0.17	kg	
Sodium perborate, monohydrate, powder, at plant/RER	0.087	kg	
Sodium perborate, tetrahydrate, powder, at plant/RER	0.115	kg	
Sodium persulfate, at plant/GLO	0.004	kg	
Sodium silicate, spray powder 80%, at plant/RER	0.03	kg	
Zeolite, powder, at plant/RER	0.201	kg	
Electricity/heat			
Electricity, high voltage, at grid/SE	0.66	kWh	
Water			
Water, ultrapure, at plant	0.142	kg	
Outputs			
Material/fuels			
Domestic washing detergent	0.943	kg	
Emissions to water			
Biological oxygen demand (BOD)	4.60E-05	kg	
Carbon dioxide, fossil	0.1254	kg	
Emissions to air			
Carbon dioxide, fossil	0.1254	kg	
Carbon monoxide, fossil	5.66E-05	kg	
COD, Chemical Oxygen Demand	9.52E-05	kg	
Dust (unspecified)	0.000166	kg	
Nitrogen oxides	0.0003102	kg	
NM VOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds, unspecified origin	0.00103	kg	
Sulphur oxides	0.0006563	kg	
Waste to treatment			
Disposal, packaging cardboard, 19.6% water, to municipal incineration	0.102	kg	
Disposal, packaging paper, 13.7% water, to municipal incineration	0.02046	kg	
Disposal, plastics, mixture, 15.3% water, to municipal incineration	0.00764	kg	

S4.9.3.4 Reimpregnation wash-in

Re-impregnation was modelled as a wash-in process. Assuming the same DWR product as used industrially. The re-impregnation was modelled separately though assumed to be one of the ordinary washes and thus no water use, or electricity was added. Emission factors from the textile industry emission scenario were applied. The jacket was assumed to be re-impregnated four times during its 5-year life length.

S4.9.4 End-of-life

The end-of-life of the jacket was modelled with municipal incineration as it was assumed that the jacket is thrown away in the ordinary garbage, which in Sweden will be incinerated at a municipal waste treatment facility. Roos et al. process waste-to-treatment (Table A2.4.1) was used as a basis for the end of life modelling, including a 0.03 tkm per kg textile incinerated.

S4.10 Ambulance jacket

The BOM of an ambulance jacket was kindly shared by a producer of such a jacket. When information was missing proxy data were assigned based on experiences in the data collection for the other garments in the project. This BOM was simplified by aggregation of materials (Table S27). The outer fabric and waterproof coating are in fact one composite material. The DWR on the outer fabric is here unspecified as this jacket provide the basis for evaluation of several different DWRs in hypothetical scenarios.

Table S27: Bill of material for the ambulance jacket

Material name	Material type	Weight in jacket (g)
Yellow outer fabric (laminate)	PES/ Membrane	440
Green outer fabric (laminate)	PA/ Membrane	190
Lining	PES	220
Tape		170
Reflex	PES/Glass beads	140
Zippers		130
Elastics and flaps	PES/Rubber	39
Labels	PES	28
Cord ends (tankas)	Acetal/PA6	28
Buttons and eyelets	Brass	23
Vliselin (non-woven)	PA 66/PES and CV/PES	18
Velcro	PA 66	16
Lining (extruded plastic)		8
Ripkit		6
Total		1400
Hanger	PS and steel	76
Plastic packaging	PE	61
Etiquettes (paper)	Paper	12
Total		1600

The membrane was modelled as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). The manufacture of PTFE can include the use of PFCAs as processing aids (Prevedouros *et al.* 2006), but their emissions were not focused on here and no adjustments were made to the PTFE manufacturing LCA dataset used.

The user scenario was that an ambulance personnel use the jacket 3 hours a day, 5 days a week, all year and in all weathers. Wash and dry at the station once a week, according to the instructions on the garment. Re-impregnation every other wash. It is not unusual that ambulance jackets are still in use after 10 years. Based on the user scenario above and discussions with Swedish ambulance personnel the durability was estimated to five years. Is often a broken zipper or similar that determines the end of life. The FU was set to 30 minutes of use to allow for relating ambulance jacket results with standard jacket results, despite the different function of the two garments.

S5 Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) additional results

Figure S3: Indicator results for the standard jacket for climate change and (eco)toxicity of the DWR alternatives normalized to indicator results of the benchmark, the C8 DWR, results for the finishing only (textile excluded). Note that results for the side-chain fluorinated polymer based DWRs were based on characterization factors based on roughly extrapolated epidemiological data and a 50% polymer degradation scenario.

S5.1 Results standard jacket per functional unit

Figure S4: Climate change indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S 5: Ecotoxicity indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S 6: Ecotoxicity indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S7: Human toxicity indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S8: Human toxicity indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S9: Eutrophication indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S10: Eutrophication indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S11: Eutrophication indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S12: Resource depletion indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S13: Resource depletion indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S14: Ozone depletion indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S15: Acidification indicator results per functional unit (FU)

Figure S16: Primary energy demand per functional unit (FU)

S5.2 Results of the scenario and uncertainty assessments on the standard jacket

Table S28: Results of the scenario assessment for the standard jacket for wash, reimpregnation and life length. All values shown are increases in indicator scores per functional unit (%) from increasing (wash, reimpregnation) or decreasing (life length) the parameter by a factor of two ($\times 2$) or ten times ($\times 10$). Hy. br. = hyperbranched polymer based DWR, C4, C6, C8 = side-chain fluorinated polymer based DWR, Si = silicone based DWR. Note that the parameters were varied independently, meaning that the $\times 10$ reimpregnation scenario would be worse in reality as the number of washes would have to be increased too (reimpregnation was modelled as a wash-in process). Life length effects were included as additional manufacture of the jacket, meaning that in the $\times 10$ scenario 10 jackets were manufactured while other parameters were held constant. Changes $<10\%$ are marked in green, $>10\% < 50\%$ in yellow and $\leq 50\%$ in red. Values rounded to one significant digit.

	Washing frequency											
	X2	X10	X2	X10	X2	X10	X2	X10	X2	X10	X2	X10
	C8	C8	C4	C4	C6	C6	Wax	Wax	Si	Si	Hy.br.	Hy.br.
Climate change	4%	30%	4%	30%	4%	30%	4%	30%	4%	30%	4%	30%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%
Ecotoxicity, marine	20%	100%	20%	100%	20%	100%	20%	100%	20%	100%	20%	100%
Human toxicity, cancer	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%	20%	200%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	1%	5%	1%	10%	1%	10%	30%	200%	10%	100%	30%	200%
	Reimpregnation frequency											
Climate change	1%	10%	1%	5%	1%	10%	1%	9%	3%	20%	0.4%	4%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	0.09%	0.8%	0.4%	4%	0.09%	0.8%	0.09%	0.8%	0.09%	0.8%	0.2%	2%
Ecotoxicity, marine	0.7%	6%	0.5%	5%	0.1%	0.9%	0.07%	0.7%	0.07%	0.6%	0.2%	2%
Human toxicity, cancer	3%	20%	0.5%	5%	2%	20%	0.3%	3%	4%	30%	0.6%	5%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	5%	40%	50%	400%	3%	30%
	Life length											
Climate change	100%	900%	100%	900%	100%	900%	100%	900%	90%	900%	100%	900%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%
Ecotoxicity, marine	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%
Human toxicity, cancer	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%	80%	700%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	20%	200%	10%	100%	20%	200%	70%	600%	40%	400%	70%	600%

Figure S17: Graphical illustrations of scenario assessment results for wash, re-impregnation and life length

Figure S18: Scenario assessment results for wash in the human toxicity non-cancer impact category

Table S29: Effect of change in emission scenarios in the standard jacket model (increase/decrease in indicator results when alt. scenario was used). Results rounded to one significant digit.

Scenario/DWR system	C4	C6	Si	Wax (emulsion)	Hyperbranched pol.
Climate change					
Low	-0.1%	-0.3%	-1%	-0.2%	-0.1%
High	1%	2%	4%	1%	1%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater					
Low	-0.1%	-0.01%	-0.02%	-0.01%	-0.05%
High	1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%
Ecotoxicity, marine					
Low	-0.2%	-0.03%	-0.01%	-0.01%	-0.04%
High	2%	0.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%
Human toxicity, cancer					
Low	-0.1%	-1%	-1%	-0.1%	-0.2%
High	1%	4%	6%	0.3%	1%
Human toxicity, non-cancer					
Low	-70%	-100%	-10%	-3%	-2%
High	600%	900%	80%	30%	20%

Table S30: Effect of change of energy source in the standard jacket model (increase/decrease in indicator results when alt. energy source was used). The electricity mix extensively used in the model basic scenario was changed into Chinese hard coal electricity or European wind electricity. Results rounded to one significant digit.

Scenario/DWR system	C4	C6	Si	Wax (emulsion)	Hyperbr. pol.
Climate change					
Wind	-40%	-40%	-40%	-40%	-40%
Coal	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater					
Wind	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
Coal	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
Ecotoxicity, marine					
Wind	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%	-50%
Coal	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
Human toxicity, cancer					
Wind	-20%	-20%	-20%	-20%	-20%
Coal	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%
Human toxicity, non-cancer					
Wind	-1%	-1%	-10%	-30%	-30%
Coal	1%	0.4%	9%	20%	20%

S5.3 Life cycle impact assessment of the ambulance jacket

The relationship between DWR systems in the cradle-to-grave ambulance jacket model were similar to those in the standard jacket model (climate change and human toxicity non-cancer indicator results in Figure S19 and additional results in Table S28). Jackets with different DWR systems had very similar predicted environmental impact in all impact categories, except for human toxicity non-cancer impacts. The toxicity non-cancer indicator scores differed between C8 and all alternatives (one order of magnitude) and between C4 and C6 and the non-fluorinated alternatives (again one order of magnitude).

In absolute terms the predicted environmental impact of the ambulance jacket was higher than those of the standard jacket. There were two main reasons to this difference, firstly the large difference in wash and reimpregnation frequency and secondly the amount of material in the jacket (the ambulance jacket was approximately 4.7 times heavier than the standard jacket).

Figure S19: Life cycle impact assessment results for the standard jacket and the ambulance jacket for climate change and human toxicity non-cancer indicators. Results are expressed per jacket over its 5-year life length. Note the broken axis in the lower diagram where the C8 ambulance jacket result was 0.15 CTUh.

S5.4 Comparison standard jacket and ambulance jacket

Table S31: Life cycle impact assessment results for the standard jacket and the ambulance jacket. Climate change (kg CO₂ eq.), toxicity (CTUh) and ecotoxicity (CTUe). Man. = manufacture, EOL=end-of-life, FW=freshwater, MW=marine water, non-c.=non-cancer.

Standard rain jacket																		
Per jacket over 5 years life length																		
	C8			C6			C4			Si			Wax (emulsion)			Hyperbr. pol.		
	Man.	Use phase	EOL	Man.	Use phase	EOL	Man.	Use phase	EOL	Man.	Use phase	EOL	Man.	Use phase	EOL	Man.	Use phase	EOL
Climate change	6.3E+00	6.0E+00	3.6E-01	-9.7E-02	6.3E+00	6.0E+00	3.6E-01	-9.7E-02	6.2E+00	6.0E+00	3.2E-01	-9.7E-02	6.4E+00	6.0E+00	4.5E-01	-9.7E-02	6.2E+00	6.0E+00
Ecotox. FW	2.8E+03	2.2E+03	5.2E+02	-9.5E-01	2.8E+03	2.2E+03	5.2E+02	-9.5E-01	2.8E+03	2.2E+03	5.3E+02	-9.5E-01	2.8E+03	2.2E+03	5.2E+02	-9.5E-01	2.8E+03	2.2E+03
Ecotox. MW	1.3E+06	1.1E+06	2.5E+05	-1.1E+02	1.3E+06	1.1E+06	2.4E+05	-1.1E+02	1.3E+06	1.1E+06	2.5E+05	-1.1E+02	1.3E+06	1.1E+06	2.4E+05	-1.1E+02	1.3E+06	1.1E+06
H.tox. cancer	2.6E-07	1.9E-07	6.1E-08	2.4E-10	2.6E-07	1.9E-07	6.0E-08	2.4E-10	2.5E-07	1.9E-07	5.5E-08	2.4E-10	2.6E-07	2.0E-07	6.3E-08	2.4E-10	2.5E-07	1.9E-07
H.tox. non-c.	2.1E-03	3.6E-04	1.7E-03	6.5E-09	4.7E-05	8.5E-06	3.8E-05	6.5E-09	2.5E-05	3.5E-06	2.2E-05	6.5E-09	2.1E-06	8.4E-07	1.2E-06	6.5E-09	8.5E-07	5.7E-07
Per 30 minutes use																		
Climate change	2.9E-03	2.8E-03	1.7E-04	-4.6E-05	2.9E-03	2.8E-03	1.7E-04	-4.6E-05	2.9E-03	2.8E-03	1.5E-04	-4.6E-05	3.0E-03	2.8E-03	2.1E-04	-4.6E-05	2.9E-03	2.8E-03
Ecotox. FW	1.3E+00	1.1E+00	2.4E-01	-4.4E-04	1.3E+00	1.1E+00	2.4E-01	-4.4E-04	1.3E+00	1.1E+00	2.5E-01	-4.4E-04	1.3E+00	1.1E+00	2.4E-01	-4.4E-04	1.3E+00	1.1E+00
Ecotox. MW	6.3E+02	5.1E+02	1.2E+02	-5.0E-02	6.2E+02	5.1E+02	1.1E+02	-5.0E-02	6.3E+02	5.1E+02	1.2E+02	-5.0E-02	6.2E+02	5.1E+02	1.1E+02	-5.0E-02	6.2E+02	5.1E+02
H.tox. cancer	1.2E-10	9.2E-11	2.9E-11	1.1E-13	1.2E-10	9.1E-11	2.8E-11	1.1E-13	1.2E-10	9.1E-11	2.6E-11	1.1E-13	1.2E-10	9.2E-11	3.0E-11	1.1E-13	1.2E-10	9.1E-11
H.tox. non-c.	9.6E-07	1.7E-07	7.9E-07	3.1E-12	2.2E-08	4.0E-09	1.8E-08	3.1E-12	1.2E-08	1.7E-09	1.0E-08	3.1E-12	9.8E-10	3.9E-10	5.9E-10	3.1E-12	4.0E-10	2.7E-10
Ambulance jacket																		
Per jacket over 5 years life length																		
Climate change	2.2E+02	3.0E+01	1.9E+02	-4.6E-01	2.2E+02	3.0E+01	1.9E+02	-4.6E-01	2.1E+02	3.0E+01	1.9E+02	-4.6E-01	2.3E+02	3.0E+01	2.0E+02	-4.6E-01	2.2E+02	3.0E+01
Ecotox. FW	4.8E+04	1.2E+04	3.7E+04	-4.5E+00	4.8E+04	1.2E+04	3.7E+04	-4.5E+00	4.9E+04	1.2E+04	3.8E+04	-4.5E+00	4.8E+04	1.2E+04	3.7E+04	-4.5E+00	4.8E+04	1.2E+04

Ecotox. MW	2.4E+07	5.6E+06	1.8E+07	-5.1E+02	2.3E+07	5.6E+06	1.7E+07	-5.1E+02	2.4E+07	5.6E+06	1.8E+07	-5.1E+02	2.3E+07	5.6E+06	1.7E+07	-5.1E+02	2.3E+07	5.6E+06
H.tox. cancer	7.6E-06	8.1E-07	6.8E-06	1.1E-09	7.5E-06	8.1E-07	6.7E-06	1.1E-09	7.0E-06	8.1E-07	6.2E-06	1.1E-09	7.8E-06	8.2E-07	6.9E-06	1.1E-09	7.0E-06	8.1E-07
H.tox. non-c.	1.5E-01	1.0E-03	1.5E-01	3.1E-08	3.4E-03	2.5E-05	3.4E-03	3.1E-08	1.8E-03	1.1E-05	1.8E-03	3.1E-08	1.2E-04	3.8E-06	1.1E-04	3.1E-08	2.3E-05	3.1E-06
Per 30 minutes use																		
Climate change	2.8E-02	3.8E-03	2.4E-02	-5.9E-05	2.8E-02	3.8E-03	2.4E-02	-5.9E-05	2.7E-02	3.8E-03	2.4E-02	-5.9E-05	2.9E-02	3.8E-03	2.5E-02	-5.9E-05	2.8E-02	3.8E-03
Ecotox. FW	6.2E+00	1.5E+00	4.7E+00	-5.8E-04	6.2E+00	1.5E+00	4.7E+00	-5.8E-04	6.3E+00	1.5E+00	4.8E+00	-5.8E-04	6.2E+00	1.5E+00	4.7E+00	-5.8E-04	6.2E+00	1.5E+00
Ecotox. MW	3.0E+03	7.2E+02	2.3E+03	-6.5E-02	2.9E+03	7.2E+02	2.2E+03	-6.5E-02	3.0E+03	7.2E+02	2.3E+03	-6.5E-02	2.9E+03	7.2E+02	2.2E+03	-6.5E-02	2.9E+03	7.2E+02
H.tox. cancer	9.7E-10	1.0E-10	8.7E-10	1.5E-13	9.6E-10	1.0E-10	8.5E-10	1.5E-13	9.0E-10	1.0E-10	8.0E-10	1.5E-13	1.0E-09	1.0E-10	8.9E-10	1.5E-13	8.9E-10	1.0E-10
H.tox. non-c.	1.9E-05	1.3E-07	1.9E-05	4.0E-12	4.3E-07	3.2E-09	4.3E-07	4.0E-12	2.4E-07	1.4E-09	2.3E-07	4.0E-12	1.5E-08	4.9E-10	1.4E-08	4.0E-12	3.0E-09	3.9E-10

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